

THE TEXTUAL HISTORY OF *EPISTULA POLYCARPI* FROM THE HISTORY OF EDITIONS TO THE BENEFITS OF THE DIGITIZED MANUSCRIPTS

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Some hundred years ago, a scholar interested in a fascinating old manuscript in a far-away library caught a train. But it was not always easy to go to the sources. Adolf Harnack wrote to Theodor Mommsen on 19 July 1897 on the problem of manuscripts of Eugippus' *Vita Severini*, which Mommsen needed for his critical edition: "Your request arrived just at the moment when I was about to send you this unfortunate piece of information that – according to the letter which I received yesterday – v. Dobschütz does not want to go to northern Italy in the fall but only for the Easter. [...] I have no one to send to northern Italy in August or September."

In the second half of the 20th century, an editor of an ancient text always had the option of taking a plane. But in the 21st century, that has very often become unnecessary. For some 25 years, more and more medieval manuscripts have been digitized, and scholars can – or at least could – consult digitized catalogues and digital libraries. Unlike in the quite recent past, scholars now have numerous manuscripts and recently hard-to-find bibliographic data at their fingertips. Despite this radical change, the full impact of the digital revolution is still to come.¹

Considering the manuscripts and editions of the so-called Apostolic Fathers, I would like to demonstrate what kind of concrete research materials and research options this change can offer. All the manuscripts, editions and most other materials I refer to can be found in my research guide on the Apostolic Fathers.² The case of the letter, which Polycarp, the bishop of Smyrna, wrote to the Christian community in Philippi (*Epistula Polycarpi*, Pol.) shortly before the martyrdom of Ignatius in 117,³ is particularly interesting. Despite important manuscript findings in the 17th and 19th centuries, no new manuscripts of this letter have been found after the Greek manuscripts appeared in the 15th century. The scholars working on the letter of Polycarp are still dependent on both Greek and Latin manuscripts because the Polycarp passage in the Greek manuscripts (1.1-9.2) does not cover the whole letter (14 chapters). Among Church Fathers, the only useful witness for the text is Eusebius, who in his Church History (3.36.13-15) quotes two passages, Pol. 9.1-2; 13.1-2. Partly because of this discouraging situation, scholars have never systematically tried to look for and assess all relevant Greek and Latin manuscripts.

Ignatius, Polycarp and Barnabas – the “Apostolic fathers” of the manuscript tradition

The expression “Apostolic fathers” and the corresponding collection of Christian writings of the second century have a complicated history (see APPENDIX). Looking at it from the angle of the

¹ For this and even more, see the inspiring book of van, Lit, L.W.C. (O.P.), *Among Digitized Manuscripts*. Philology, Codicology, Paleography in a Digital World. Leiden: Brill 2020. – The present article is a slightly revised version of the original published with the same title in *Kniha 2020: Zborník o problémoch a dejinách knižnej kultúry*. Bratislava: Slovenská národná knižnica, p. 9-35.

² Manuscripts Evidence: The Apostolic Fathers [online]. [cit.2020-8-31]. Available from: <https://libraryguides.helsinki.fi/apostolicfathers>. In the footnotes, I refer to the articles and books indexed in the research guide in a simple form (e. g., BAUER 1995, 18–21). The bibliography in the end of this article includes printed materials as well as articles and books, which are digitally available, but behind pay walls and not included in the research guide. In the footnotes, I introduce them with full bibliographic information.

³ There is a trend to divide Pol. in two letters, ch. 1–12 and 13–14; see BAUER, Johannes Baptist. *Die Polykarpbriefe*. Kommentar zu den Apostolischen Vätern 5. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck u. Ruprecht 1995, 18–21. For the unity of the letter argues GLEEDE, Benjamin. *Parabiblica Latina: Studien zu den griechisch-lateinischen Übersetzungen parabiblicher Literatur unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der apostolischen Väter*. Vigiliae Christianae, Supplements 137. Leiden: Brill 2016.

manuscript tradition, the letters of Ignatius, Polycarp and Barnabas form the historical kernel of this early modern literary canon. Ignatius was the bishop of Antioch, who flourished in the times of Trajan, and his friend Polycarp was the bishop of Smyrna; they both died as martyrs in Rome. The letter of Barnabas, in turn, was written by an unknown Alexandrian teacher in the first half of the second century and some decades later attributed to the co-worker of Paul known from Paul’s letters and the Acts of the Apostles. In numerous Greek and Latin manuscripts, their corresponding writings have been transmitted together in different combinations. I shall first open the different sets of manuscripts and list them with help of modern digital catalogues and digital libraries.

Ignatius wrote seven letters to Christian communities in Asia Minor, and one of these letters he addressed to Polycarp, the bishop of Smyrna. In the late fourth century, these letters were edited, and some new, completely spurious letters were composed to carry the celebrated name of this early orthodox bishop and martyr. The result was the so-called long recension of Ignatian letters – theologically close to the Apostolic Constitutions – which was transmitted first in Greek and later in Latin translation:

TABLE 1. The Making of the Canon of the Ignatian Letters

Original letters	Edited & new letters	The long recension
Smyrn.	Smyrn.	Trall.
Polyk.	Polyk.	Magn.
Ef.	Ef.	Tars.
Magn.	Magn.	Fil.
Filad.	Filad.	Filad.
Trall.	Trall.	Smyrn.
	Tars.	Polyk.
	Ant.	Ant.
	Her.	Her.
	Fil.	Ef.
	Mart. Ign.	
Room.	Room.	Room.

From the very beginning, the original letter of Ignatius to the Romans was transmitted as an appendix to the martyrdom of Ignatius; it remained unchanged among manuscripts containing martyrdom stories. When it was joined to the long recension of other letters from Ignatius, it was edited like other letters. In all the Greek manuscripts we know from the Middle Ages, the Ignatian letters are transmitted without the letter of Polycarp.⁴ The key witness of the long recension up to the end of the 19th century was a tenth-century manuscript (München, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, gr. 394).⁵ Leaning on this manuscript alone, it was possible to publish printed editions of the Ignatian corpus, starting with the Greek text published by Valentinus Paccus in Dillingen (1557) and the synoptic edition of the Greek original and Latin translation by Andreas Gesnerus in Zurich (1559 – 1560).⁶ In the times of reformation, almost everybody thought that these were the original second-century letters of the renowned bishop of Antioch.

As for the Latin manuscripts, the situation was different. Western medieval scholars knew the letters of Ignatius from manuscripts, which include twelve letters, starting with the completely spurious letter

⁴ For the Greek manuscripts including both the long recension of the Ignatian corpus as well the mutilated “Polycarnabas”, see below.

⁵ On the other two manuscripts that were found later, see below.

⁶ The edition Paccus was more popular than that of Gesnerus, and editions before Ussher and Voss based their Greek text on the work of Paccus; on these editions, see LIGHTFOOT, II.3 (1890), 132.

to Maria the Proselyte and ending with the letter to the Romans, plus Laus Heronis. These are followed by the letter of Polycarp, which, unlike the Ignatian corpus, was not edited at all, but translated directly from the Greek original. The oldest of these manuscripts is Reginensis (r; 9th century) in the Vatican Library (Reg.lat.81). Looking from the present digital perspective, there are at least 22 Latin manuscripts, which include both the long recension of the Ignatian letters and the letter of Polycarp (see TABLE 3).⁷ We still do not know of any Latin manuscripts, which would include only either of them alone.

In 1498, Jacques Lefèvre d'Étaples (Jacobus Faber Stapulensis; c. 1455 – 1536) published in Paris the first edition of the Latin text of the Ignatian long recension and the letter of Polycarp as an appendix to his edition of the Pseudo-Dionysian writings. For almost 150 years, the following editions of Ignatius and Polycarp leaned on his text, and his book was reprinted in Strasbourg (1502, 1527), Paris (1515), Basel (1520), Cologne (1536) and Venice (1537).⁸ Scholars have not been sure, which manuscript Lefèvre d'Étaples used for the Ignatian corpus and the letter of Polycarp.⁹ On the basis of comparison to all known manuscripts, it is clear that Lefèvre d'Étaples drew upon manuscripts, which belonged to family β . In northern France, there were at least four manuscripts of this family available at that time.¹⁰

With the 14th-century renaissance and the final collapse of the remains of the once-great Byzantine Empire in 1453, Greek manuscripts started to flow to the West. Among the original Greek manuscripts of the Church Fathers, scholars also found the long recension of the letters of Ignatius joined with the letter of Polycarp. Most librarians, clergymen and even scholars did not see that there was something strange with the letter of Polycarp in these manuscripts, which had been copied quite recently and which were now innocently reproduced in the Roman libraries and archives. This letter of Polycarp was not simply the Greek original, and it took some time to notice that somewhere before half of the letter, in the middle of a line, the writing of Polycarp ended and something else was copied instead, up to the end of the letter. The unknown part was the letter of Barnabas missing its beginning. Put in modern chapters and verses, the presumed *Epistula Polycarpi* was actually Pol. 1.1-9.2 + Barn. 5.7-21.9.

Some of these Greek manuscripts were produced in the 15th century, but most of them are 16th-century copies. In the digital catalogues, there are six manuscripts, which include both the Ignatian letters of the long recension and the mutilated “Polycarnabas”; these manuscripts are interrelated, and they are called family α . All these manuscripts have been digitized. In addition, there are nine manuscripts including the “Polycarnabas” without the Ignatian letters preceding it (family β). These manuscript groups also represent two clearly different branches or families in the manuscript tradition, family α being closer to the original text than family β (see TABLE 2).

⁷ Eleven of these manuscripts have not been mentioned even by the most recent editors; GLEEDE (ref. 3, p. 364) talks about “twelve known manuscripts”.

⁸ The edition of Lefèvre d'Étaples was also copied for the monastery of St. Emmeran in Bavaria; the copy is in Bavarian State Library in Munich (Clm 14089) and is also available in digitized form. Another 16th century copy of this edition is preserved in Ferrara (Biblioteca comunale Ariostea, Cl. II. 231). The database Manus Online introduces Lefèvre d'Étaples here as “commentatore”.

⁹ LIGHTFOOT (II.3 [1890], 318) who among the editor of the Apostolic fathers seems to be best informed about manuscripts traditions, remains unsure: “It is not known what MS or MSS Faber Stapulensis used.”

¹⁰ It is possible that Lefèvre d'Étaples used Colbertinus, a 12th century manuscript donated by John of Burgundy in the 15th century to the monastery of the Celestines in Ternes. Two particular readings seem to speak for such a conclusion: rogo igitur in 9.2 (other mss. in family β read rogo ergo) and quomodo alii pronuntiat hoc in 11.2 (a reading found in c alone). However, in 1.3 Lefèvre d'Étaples clearly follows the truncated reading facti estis (with t) instead of the correct reading salvi facti estis known from c o cm. Furthermore, in 12.2 in Lefèvre d'Étaples reads with all other manuscripts of family β dominum nostrum (b d o t v) against dominum, the short reading preserved by c alone. Therefore, it seems more likely that Lefèvre d'Étaples used also another family β manuscript, possibly a lost one; see Funk 1901, XCVI.

TABLE 2**Epistula Polycarpi Graeca****family α (Ign. long recension + Pol. 1.1-9.2 + Barn. 5.7-21.9)**

Vaticanus (v)	s.XV	Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Vat.Gr.859 D
Ottobonianus (o)	s.XV	Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Ott.Gr.348 D
Florentinus (f)	s.XV/XVI	Firenze, Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana, Plut. 7.21 D
Parisinus (p)	s.XVI	Paris, Bibliothèque nationale de France, Grec 937 D
g	s.XVI	Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Ott.gr.378 D
Eblanus (e)	s.XVI	Dublin, Trinity College, ms. 219 D

family β (Pol. 1.1-9.2 + Barn. 5.7-21.9)

Neapolitanus (n)	s.XV/XVI	Napoli, Biblioteca Nazionale, II. A. 17
Theatinus (t)	s.XV/XVI	Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Reg.gr.Pio.II.11
Casatanensis (c)	s.XVI	Roma, Biblioteca Casanatense, ms. 334
Andros (a)	s.XVI	Andros, Monê Hagias (Zôodochou Pêgês), ms. 64
d	s.XVI	Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Vat.gr.1655
Barberinus (b)	s.XVI	Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Barb.gr.511 D
h	s.XVI	Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Ott.gr.449 D
Romanus (r)	s.XVI	Roma, Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, Greci 1
Vallensis (s)	s.XVI	Roma, Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, S. A. Valle 100

Copies of the editors

Vossius	s.XVII	Bibliotheek der Rijksuniversiteit, Voss. gr. O° 16
Menardensis	s.XVII	Paris, Bibliothèque nationale de France, Suppl. grec 830
Oxon. Bodleianus (ob)	s.XVII	Oxford, Bodleian Library, Cherr 31 (Ussher?)
Oxon. Reginensis (oq)	s.XVII	Oxford, Queen's College, ms. 186 (Ussher?)

TABLE 3**Epistula Polycarpi : Manuscripta Latina****(Ign. long recension + Pol.)****family α**

Reginensis (r)	s. IX	Vatican, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Reg.lat.81 D
Atrebatensis (a)	s. XI	Arras, Médiathèque municipale, ms. 51 D
Carolopolitanus α (c α)	s. XII	Charleville-Mezieres, Bibliothèque municipale, ms.266 D
Palatinus (p)	s. XV	Vatican, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Pal.Lat.150 D
Oxon. Magdalensis (m)	s. XV	Oxford, Magdalene College, ms. 76
Florentinus (f)	s. XV	Firenze, Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana, Plut. 23.20 D
Urbanus (u)	s. XV	Vatican, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Urb.Lat.486 D
*Matritensis α (m α)	s. XV	Madrid, Biblioteca Nacional, ms. 7126 D
*Vaticanus 1 (v1)	s. XV	Vatican, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Vat.lat.186 D
*Vaticanus 2 (v2)	s. XV	Vatican, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Vat.lat.303 D

family β

Bruxellensis (b)	s. XI	Brussels, Bibliothèque Royale de Belgique, ms. 1024
Colbertinus (c)	s. XII	Paris, Bibliothèque nationale de France, latin 1639 D
*Remensis (r β)	s. XII	Reims, Bibliothèque municipale, ms. 82 D
Oxon. Balliolensis (o)	s. XII	Oxford, Colleg. Baliol. 229 D
Trecensis (t)	s. XII	Troyes, Médiathèque, ms. 412 D
Carolopolitanus β (c β)	s. XII	Charleville-Mezieres, Bibliothèque municipale, ms.173 D
*Matritensis b (m β)	s. XIV	Madrid, Biblioteca Nacional, ms 437 D
Vindobonensis (v)	s. XIV	Wien, Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, Cod. 1068
Bruxellensis (bm)	s. XV	Brussels, Bibliothèque Royale de Belgique, ms. 1034
Bruxellensis (bn)	s. XVI	Brussels, Bibliothèque Royale de Belgique, ms. 905

unclassified manuscripts

*Bruxellensis (bq)	s. XV	Brussels, Bibliothèque Royale de Belgique, ms. IV 537
*Senensis (s)	s. ?	Siena, Biblioteca Comunale degli Intronati, E.IV.16 XV.1

On the basis of the Greek and Latin manuscripts we know it can be concluded that in one branch of Greek manuscripts, the letter of Polycarp was copied together with the long recension of the Ignatian letters. Only relatively late, much closer to the 15th century, the letter of Barnabas was added after the Ignatian corpus and the letter of Polycarp in some Greek manuscripts. Most likely and as far we know, only one manuscript of this text form was preserved and transmitted to the West, and this particular manuscript was missing a quarto – eight pages of text.¹¹ Correspondingly, before the end of the 19th century, the Greek text of the letter of Barnabas was not known in the West, and its Latin translation passed virtually unknown because it was poorly distributed and seldom copied.¹²

The Greek-Latin Editions of the 17th Century

The Greek manuscripts of *Epistula Polycarpi* were known from the 16th century, but it took some time before the Greek edition became public. In 1633, the Jesuit scholar Pierre Halloix (1572 – 1656) published a synopsis of the Greek and Latin text in his *Illustrium ecclesiae orientalis scriptorium*.¹³ As for the Greek original, he says that he used two copies of manuscripts, one that was made in Rome by Turrianus (Francisco Torres; c. 1509 – 1584), a Spanish Jesuit Hellenist and polemicist, copied and transmitted to Halloix by Jacques Sirmond (1559 – 1651).¹⁴ The other manuscript also stemmed from Rome and was copied there by André Schott (Andreas Schottus; 1552 – 1629); his copy, in turn, was copied by Claude Saumaise (Claudius Salmasius; 1588 – 1653), a French classical scholar, who delivered it to Halloix.¹⁵ The edition of Halloix reveals that the manuscripts he used stem from two different families.¹⁶ If we trace them by following the readings of the edition, the most likely candidates are Vaticanus (v) and Casatanensis (c).¹⁷ Of course, here we enter the realm of speculation, because scribal errors may also have played their role in the process of transmission. Be as it may, for the Latin translation Halloix did not use manuscripts but translated the Greek text by himself. He did not publish the letter of Barnabas from the latter half of his “Polycarnabas” manuscripts, because in the 730 pages of his work he wanted to present the documents reflecting the exemplary life of saints who also were known as authors. For him, the Martyrdom of Polycarp was even more important than the letter.

Some scholars had early discovered that the text of the long recension of the letters of Ignatius did not match with the quotations of these letters in the writings of the Church fathers. In the 16th century, they concluded that there has been a shorter, original version of Ignatius’ letters, which was edited and supplemented at a much later time. In the 1640s, three text discoveries confirmed the suspicion and laid the foundations for the publication of Ignatius’ genuine letters. In England, the exiled archbishop of Ireland, James Ussher (1581 – 1656) – the same man who dated the creation of the world to the year 4004 B.C. – searched and found two manuscripts containing, in addition to the forged letters, the old Latin translation of the original seven letters of Ignatius. Of these two manuscripts, the so-called Montacutianus has disappeared, while the other has survived in Cambridge (Caius College, ms. 395). Ussher compared the manuscripts to the Ignatian quotations of Eusebius,

¹¹ See PROSTMEIER, Ferdinand 1999. Der Barnabasbrief. Übersetzung und Kommentar. Kommentar zu den Apostolischen Vätern. Ergänzungsreihe zum Kritisch-exegetischen Kommentar über das Neue Testament, Bd. 8. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht 1999. P. 48-49 and 58 (n. 7).

¹² On the two Latin manuscripts including the letter of Barnabas and found by James Ussher in 1640’s, see below.

¹³ HALLOIX 1633, 525-532.

¹⁴ Hugo Ménard also used this copy for his *edition princeps* of the letter of Barnabas (Paris 1645).

¹⁵ LIGHTFOOT II.2, 316 names this copy as Salmasianus (s) among his Greek manuscripts.

¹⁶ Pace LIGHTFOOT III.2: 319.

¹⁷ The edition of Halloix often agrees with c and family β; see Praescr. κυρίου Ἰησοῦ Χριστοῦ (n t c a b h); 1.1 ἐν κυρίῳ (n t c a b h); ἐνελημμένους (p c); 2.1 ὁσφύας (n t c a b h); 5.2 μὴ διγλώσσοι (c t a b); 6.2 ὑπὲρ ἑαυτοῦ (c t n b h); 6.3 οἱ εὐαγγελιστάμενοι ἡμᾶς (n t c a b h); σκανδάλων (n t c a b h); 8. 2 τῆς ὑπομονῆς αὐτοῦ (c t n** a b h). However, the edition of Halloix also agrees at least five times with the manuscripts of family α; see 2.1 λατρεύει, (v); πορευόμεθα (v o (t) f a g h e); 4.1 διδάξωμεν (v o f p g e); 4.2 γυναῖκας ὑμῶν (v f b h); 8.2 δοξάζομεν (v o* p); 9.1 ἐν ἀντῶ (v o f p g e Eus). The passage of Eusebius may also have influenced the Greek text of Halloix.

Theodoretus, and other fathers and found them to be based on the original letters. Thus in 1644, Ussher published in Oxford the first edition of the seven genuine letters from Ignatius. It was a synopsis of the Latin text and the Greek original text reconstructed from the letters of the long recension and quotations from the Church fathers. He added the letter to the Romans in the form of a long recension. He opened his edition with the Greek text of the letter of Polycarp and its Latin translation. On this edition, he says that he has used the edition of Halloix and the transcript of Andreas Schottus; thus he actually reproduces the text of Halloix.¹⁸ As for the Latin text, Ussher relied on Reginensis (r) and two manuscripts he found in Oxford, Magdalensis (m) and Balliolensis (o).¹⁹ The present division of the letter in fourteen chapters stems from Ussher's division of the letter in fourteen passages.

In 1641 Isaac Voss, son of Dutch humanist Gerhard Johann Vossius and passionate hunter of old manuscripts made a long European tour in England, France and Italy. Voss stayed long in Florence, where he made a copy of the last folios of an 11th-century manuscript, which includes six original letters of Ignatius, followed by the forged correspondence between Ignatius and Mary, and an equally spurious letter to the Christian community in Tarsos (Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana, Plut. 57.7, f. 242r-252v). On his return to Paris in July 1643, Voss made his discovery known to many scholars. The manuscript did not include Ignatius' letter to the Romans, which, as mentioned above, was transmitted with the story of Ignatius' martyrdom. From now on, the editions of Ignatius' letters were entirely dependent on this manuscript now called Medicea. In Rome, there are four copies of the Ignatian epistles of Medicea. The oldest of them is a 16th-century copy preserved in the Biblioteca Casanatense (ms. 334), while three others can be found in Vatican libraries (Ott.gr.194; Ott.gr.272; Barb.gr.511; all of them digitized). These Vatican manuscripts were most likely written at the time Voss made his discovery. These four copies reflect the great interest in Medicea – although the copyists did not leave forged letters uncopied.

In 1646, Isaac Voss published in Amsterdam his edition of both the seven genuine and the twelve spurious letters of Ignatius, joining in an edition of the truncated Greek text of the letter of Barnabas, which he based on three manuscripts: Vaticanus, Florentinus and Theatinus.²⁰ He could have used the same manuscripts to publish an edition of the letter of Polycarp as well, but he did not, because he had made an agreement with Ussher. The edition of Voss opened a quite new future for Ignatian studies: the long recension was set aside, and scholars focused on the original letters instead.

The first edition of the letter of Barnabas was prepared by Nicolas-Hugues Ménard (Hugo Menardus; 1585 – 1644), a French Benedictine scholar, whose work was published in Paris after his death in 1645.²¹ Menard used the newly discovered medieval Latin translation, the text of which ends in verse 17.2, the Greek “Polycarnabas”, which begins with verse 5.7, and quotations from Greek Church fathers, especially Clemens of Alexandria. Like Halloix, Menard received his Greek “Polycarnabas” from the Jesuit father Jacques Sirmond, who got it from Turrianus (see above).²²

¹⁸ LIGHTFOOT, III.2: 319. In Pol. 4.2, in which the most likely original reading of a difficult wording is πάντα μομοσκοπεῖται, Ussher reads with Halloix and against all manuscripts πάντα ἡμῶν σκοπεῖται.

¹⁹ LIGHTFOOT, I.2: 126-127, 129-130; also FUNK 1901, XCVI.

²⁰ The edition of Voss was reprinted in London 1680 and Oxford 1708.

²¹ In England, in 1644, James Ussher also prepared an edition using the same source material. He planned to publish it as a part of his edition of the letters of Ignatius and Polycarp. However, the Barnabas part of the edition was destroyed in the great fire at Oxford on 6th October before the printing work was started. When Ménard had published his edition, Ussher saw no reason to work on his own edition anymore. Over 200 years later, John Harris Backhouse found the lost edition of Ussher and published it with an interesting introduction.

²² In the foreword of his edition Ménard says: “Unde autem exsciperit apographum Thurrianus? Res est nobis prorsus ignota.” – It should also be noted that Pinakes has listed among the manuscripts of the letter of Barnabas Ott. gr. 32

After the revolutionary developments in the 1640's, the editions of the writings of the apostolic fathers were based on the work of the predecessors. For some 200 years, no one was interested in going back to the manuscripts or looking for new ones.²³ Joachim Maders (1626 – 1680), a historian active in Helmstedt, was the first scholar to publish an edition of the letter of Polycarp in Germany (*Ad Philippenses epistola una cum ejusdem martyrio et tam veterum quam recentiorum testimoniis*, Helmstedt 1653). He used the editions of Halloix and Ussher, whose critical text lived on also in Cotelier's groundbreaking work *SS. Patrum qui temporibus apostolicis floruerunt* (Paris 1672), and in its subsequent editions by Leclerc (Antwerpen 1698, Amsterdam 1724) and Russel (London 1746). The first edition of the Apostolic fathers – i. e., the letters of Clement, Ignatius and Polycarp – to appear in Germany (*Bibliotheca Patrum Apostolicorum Graeco-Latina*, Leipzig 1699), was published by the Lutheran theologian Thomas Ittig (1643 – 1710), who drew for the most upon the edition of Cotelier. In the Roman Catholic world, it was characteristic to collect and publish all the patristic literature under a single title; the most important of these collections were made in France by André Galland (*Bibliotheca veterum patrum*, 1765 – 81) and Jacques Paul Migne (*Patrologia Graeca*, 1857 – 66). The expression and collection of the Apostolic fathers became universally accepted only during the 19th century.

Back to the Manuscripts: Developments in the 19th Century

In 1838, William Jacobson (1803 – 1884), the Regius Professor of Divinity at Oxford University, published his edition on the letters of Clement, Ignatius and Polycarp.²⁴ Jacobson, who could not yet enjoy the comfort of travelling in trains, studied manuscripts in Florence, Rome, Paris and Vienna. He based his edition of Polycarp's letter on three Greek manuscripts (v, p, f) and three Latin manuscripts (c, o, f). Jacobson comments on the Greek text but also provides the Latin text with a selection of variant readings.

Soon afterwards, two Catholic scholars in Germany published their own editions of the Apostolic Fathers. They both wanted to bring to the bookstores an affordable and easily accessible edition of the important second-century writings, which at the time were unavailable in Germany. They did not study the manuscripts but based their texts on the best available editions. In 1839, Karl Josef von Hefele (1809 – 1893), who had just become the ordinary professor of Church History in Tübingen, published his *Patrum apostolicorum opera*. He became the first editor to join the letter to Diognetus among the writings of the Apostolic Fathers. Hefele published only the Greek text of each writing, filling the gaps in the letters of Barnabas and Polycarp with the old Latin translations. His work was republished three times (1842, 1847, 1855).²⁵ The edition of Franz Xaver Reithmayr (1809–1872), professor of the New Testament in Munich, was less popular.²⁶ Like Hefele, Reithmayr drew upon the best previous editions, but also provided the Latin text.

All these editions demonstrate that there was a renewed interest in the original works of the Apostolic Fathers. However, the real turn of the tide came with a new manuscript found in the monastery of Saint Catherine on Mount Sinai. In 1844, Konstantin Tischendorf discovered there what we now

from the Vatican Library. This manuscript includes writing from "Cypriot Barnabas" (f. 37rv), but it is a completely different text from later times.

²³ LIGHTFOOT, II.3: 132–133. He mentions that Cotelier collated some readings from Supplement grec 341 in the French national library. These were, in turn, reproduced by Whiston, who in his edition from 1711 otherwise completely relied on the text of Voss.

²⁴ S. Clementis Romani, S. Ignatii, S. Polycarpi, Patrum Apostolicorum, quae supersunt, accedunt S. Ignatii et S. Polycarpi Martyria. Oxford (2 vols). This work became very popular, and altogether three successive editions were published: 1840, 1847 and 1863. For his own presentation of the book, see his short article (HEFELE 1839).

²⁵ In 1869, Hefele became the Roman Catholic bishop of Rottenburg.

²⁶ Patrum apostolicorum S. Clementis Rom., S. Barnabae, S. Ignatii et S. Polycarpi epistolae : accedunt S. Ignatii et S. Polycarpi martyria.

know as Sinaiticus, the single most important manuscript of the Bible. The 4th century manuscript, published as a facsimile in 1862, also included the text of two writings counted to the collection of the Apostolic Fathers: the letter of Barnabas as a whole and the Shepherd of Hermas, lacking only the end of the book of Visions (Sim. IX 18).

The first editor of the Apostolic Fathers to draw upon Sinaiticus was Albert Dressel (1808 – 1875), who moved to Rome as a young man and lived there with his Italian wife and children for the rest of his life. The discovery of Sinaiticus was the ultimate motivation for Dressel to publish his *Patrum apostolicorum opera*, and in his preface, he thanked Tischendorf for his permission to study the manuscript. The first edition of Dressel's work was published in Leipzig in 1857 (2nd edition 1863). From now on, the text of the letter of Barnabas – with which Dressel opens his edition – was based on Sinaiticus, and the mutilated “Polycarnabas” manuscripts became secondary. As for the letter of Polycarp (and for the long recension of the Ignatian epistles), Dressel introduced three Greek manuscripts from the Roman libraries not used by Jacobson (v f p + o c b). For his Latin text, Dressel used Regius (r) and Palatinus (p), both available to him in Rome.²⁷ The presence of an active German scholar in Rome, close to the Vatican libraries, was a good start for renewed study of manuscripts of the writings of Clement, Ignatius, Polycarp and others.²⁸

In 1876, the famous Protestant specialist on early Christian literature Theodor Zahn (1838 – 1933), published his edition of the Ignatian epistles and the letter of Polycarp. He was the first scholar to recognize that the Greek manuscripts of these letters belong to two different families. Manuscripts v, o, f, p are closely related and belong to family α , while several readings in manuscripts n, t, c, a, and b demonstrate that they together deviate from the common readings of family α . Thus, they belong to family β .²⁹ Zahn also introduced a Greek translation of the Latin text in 9.2–14, but he provided the Latin text only for passages lacking the Greek original. Otto von Gebhardt and Adolf von Harnack reworked the edition launched by Zahn up to the 6th edition, which appeared in 1920, still with a Latin title and introduction.

In 1880, Franz Xaver Funk (1840 – 1907), professor of Catholic theology at Tübingen, published a short article, which was destined to change the study of the manuscripts of the long recension of the Ignatian corpus and the letter of Polycarp for good. In his long and extensive studies for his edition of the former, he ended up with the insight that all the Greek manuscripts of the Ignatian corpus and “Polycarnabas” are copies based on one single manuscript, namely Vaticanus (v; Vat.gr.859).³⁰ His conclusion, embraced by all scholars studying these manuscripts today, was that Ottobonianus (o) is a copy of Vaticanus, and Florentinus (f), in turn, is a copy of Ottobonianus, while Palatinus (p) was copied from Florentinus. Funk worked out his textual findings in *Opera Patrum apostolicorum* (2 vols., 1878 – 1881; 2nd ed., 1901).

Joseph Barber Lightfoot (1828 – 1889) was a Lady Margaret's Professor of Divinity in Cambridge (1875–1879) and bishop of Durham (1875–1889) who wrote an extensive edition, study, and commentary of the letters of Clement, Ignatius and Polycarp. Even though he could build upon the work of Dressel, Zahn, Funk and others, his introductions to the manuscripts of these letters surpassed

²⁷ He discarded Florentinus (f), which was preferred by Jacobson.

²⁸ Dressel also edited the Pseudoclementine Homilies in 1853, after having found a new, complete 16th century manuscript in the Ottobonian library (Ott.gr.443). Before his edition, scholars were completely dependent on editions based on a 10th century manuscript (Bibliothèque nationale de France, grec 930) missing the end of the text.

²⁹ Neapolitanus (n) was identified and collated by Gebhardt, who shared his findings with Zahn. Because Zahn's edition was already prepared for printing, he could merely note this in his preface (p. XLVI).

³⁰ FUNK, Franz Xaver. “Der Codex Vaticanus gr. 859 und seine Descendenten”. *Theologische Quartalschrift* 62 (1880), p. 629-637.

the work of his predecessors in clarity, pervasiveness, and scope. As for the Ignatian long recension and the letter of Polycarp, Lightfoot listed altogether eight Greek and fourteen Latin manuscripts:³¹

Greek manuscripts	v o f p / n t c a
Latin manuscripts	r p m f / b c o t v / cp cm a bm bn

Lightfoot followed the division of the Greek manuscripts in two groups (rather than families, he speaks of “subdivisions”). From family β, he knew also Barberinus (b), but neither listed nor used it. For his edition, Lightfoot used nine Latin manuscripts (r t b c o p f v m). He left out both manuscripts of the library of Charleville-Mezieres (ca and cβ) and the Arras manuscript (a) because he knew them only from the library catalogues and was not able to collate them. He also left out two manuscripts from the Royal Library of Brussels (bm and bn), which he collated, but did not use, except for one reading in ch. 13.³² He found out that these late manuscripts were both copies of b – bm directly and bn directly or indirectly. Excepting the affordable edition of Hefele, Lightfoot’s edition was the first edition to discard the Latin text of Polycarp as parallels for the Greek text (1.1-9.2 and the parallel text of Eusebius for ch. 13); this practice soon became a rule for modern editions. Independently of Zahn, Lightfoot also translated the Latin text of the other, missing parts into Greek. Encouraged by “the very general agreement” of the two translations he concludes that “they fairly represent the original of Polycarp”.³³

In its present form, the writings of the Apostolic Fathers appeared for the first time in the edition of Franz Xaver Funk. His *Patres apostolici* (Tübingen & Leipzig 1901) included – in addition to the works of the Hefele edition – the recently found Didache (The teaching of the Apostles) and the fragments of Quadratus and Papias which are known from the Church History of Eusebius. Funk separated the Ignatian long recension clearly from the corpus of the Apostolic Fathers and published it in the second volume including also other later and spurious writings.³⁴ He also drew the editorial consequences from his analysis of the Greek manuscripts of the letter of Polycarp and divided them for the apparatus in two groups, Vaticanus (G) and manuscripts dependent on Vaticanus (G2, “codicis secunda manus”). Unlike Lightfoot, he provides the Latin text without apparatus, marking the best readings of the Latin text in the Greek apparatus with L. In his German edition (*Die apostolischen Väter*, Tübingen & Leipzig 1901), Funk gave up the manuscript apparatus completely and offered only the critical text. He also dispensed with the Latin text as a parallel to the original Greek. This edition was about to become *the* source of Apostolic Fathers for all German and many other continental *Neutestamentler* as well as other theologians of the 20th century. It was reworked and reprinted several times throughout the century (1906, 1913, 1924 (ed. by Bihlmeyer), 1956, 1970, 1992 (Shepherd of Hermas added)).³⁵

In the English-speaking world, the edition of Lightfoot was as influential as that of Funk in Germany. Soon after the death of Lightfoot, J. R. Harmer reworked and published it as a shortened and practical version in 1891. The new edition included brief introductions, critical text, and translations. Harmer also added other writings included in the collection of the Apostolic Fathers.³⁶ The edition of Harmer

³¹ For the Latin manuscripts, see LIGHTFOOT, I.2: 125-134.

³² LIGHTFOOT, II.3: 318.

³³ LIGHTFOOT, II.3: 320.

³⁴ *Clementis Romani epistulae de virginitate eiusdemque martyrium, epistulae Pseudoignatii, Ignatii martyria, fragmenta Polycarpiana, Polycarpi vita*. Tübingen & Leipzig, 1913.

³⁵ A French edition of the letters of Ignatius and Polycarp: Auguste LELONG 1927. *Les Pères apostoliques, vol. III : Ignace d'Antioche et Polycarpe de Smyrne*. Its critical text is based on the edition of Funk.

³⁶ *The Apostolic Fathers: comprising the epistles (genuine and spurious) of Clement of Rome, the epistles of S. Ignatius, the epistle of S. Polycarp, the martyrdom of S. Polycarp, the teaching of the Apostles, the epistle of Barnabas, the Sheperd of Hermas, the epistle to Diognetus, the fragments of Papias, the reliques of the elders preserved in Irenæus*.

was reprinted several times, and in 1992, Michael Holmes published a revised critical edition, which has become a new standard edition in the global village. Also, the Loeb edition of the Apostolic Fathers by Kirsopp Lake (2 vols.; London 1912 and 1913) was reprinted several times up to 1965. Lake chose the critical editions he followed separately for each writing; for the letter of Polycarp, he followed the text of Lightfoot. The Loeb edition was completely revised by Bart Ehrman (2 vols.; London 2003). As textual witnesses for the letter of Polycarp Ehrman mentions the manuscripts used by Lightfoot and adds Andros (a); for the Latin translation, he names nine witnesses without classifying them (r, t, c, b, o, p, f, v, m). For the “combined witness of the nine defective Greek manuscripts” he uses the letter G, and for the “combined witness of the Latin manuscripts,” he uses the letter L.³⁷ In the footnotes of his critical text, he offers variant readings in eighteen instances. In 2013, Paul Hartog, a specialist on Polycarp, published an edition of the letter and the Martyrdom of Polycarp. In his brief introduction to the textual witnesses,³⁸ he names eight Greek manuscripts used by Lightfoot. He says – following Lightfoot – that the Latin translation is preserved in thirteen or fourteen manuscripts. The edition of Hartog has the Greek text with translation and the Latin text with translation for the passages where the Greek original is not available. His work has a good, but not exhaustive textual apparatus.

In recent times, scholars have collated some of the neglected manuscripts. In his article from 1994, Ferdinand R. Prostmeier, a specialist on the letter of Barnabas and its textual criticism, presents the Greek manuscript d (Vat.gr.1655, which has not been digitized yet) as a descendant of Vaticanus, which Funk had proven to be the father of all known “Polycarnabas” manuscripts. Based on the text of the letter of Barnabas, Prostmeier concludes from his observations that d is closely related to n and t, and also to c and a.³⁹

The most recent contribution to the manuscript tradition of the letter of Polycarp comes from Benjamin Gleede, who has explored the Latin manuscript tradition and collated two manuscripts that scholars have discarded until now.⁴⁰ He notes that there are twelve known manuscripts. The hitherto used manuscripts of family α are r, p, m, f and of family β they are b, c, o, t, v.⁴¹ Gleede collates Artabatensis (a; for him, Arras 51 [A]) and Carolopolitanus β (c β ; for him, Charlesville 173 [C]) for 33 key disagreements between manuscripts of families α and β . He concludes that the text of family α represented by a, r, p and possibly also m and f offer a clearly better text than the here and there edited manuscripts of family β (c β , c, o and most likely v, b, t). He also notes that the text of Palatinus (p) is corrupted in relation to the better witnesses r and a, and therefore it is questionable whether it really belongs to family α .

The History of Transmission of *Epistula Polycarpi*: Towards the Whole Picture

The digital catalogues and the digitization of the manuscripts have made it possible to go beyond the point reached by Prostmeier and Gleede. As for the Greek manuscripts (see TABLE 2), it is possible to assess the evidence and conclude that all the manuscripts we know can be divided into two families. Concerning the clear basic differences between families α and β , I have collated the readings of family

Revised texts with short introductions and English translations by the late J. B. LIGHTFOOT ; edited and completed by J. R. HARMER.

³⁷ EHRMAN, Bart (ed. and trans.), *The Apostolic Fathers*. Vols. 1-2. Loeb Classical Library 24-25. Harvard University Press 2003. Vol. I, p. 330.

³⁸ HARTOG, Paul. *Polycarp's Epistle to the Philippians and the Martyrdom of Polycarp: Introduction, Text, and Commentary*. Oxford University Press 2013. P. 26-27.

³⁹ P PROSTMEIER, Ferdinand. *Der Barnabasbrief*. Übersetzung und Kommentar. Kommentar zu den Apostolischen Vätern. Ergänzungsreihe zum Kritisch-exegetischen Kommentar über das Neue Testament, Bd. 8. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1999. P. 51-52.

⁴⁰ GLEEDE, ref. 3, p. 364-368.

⁴¹ I have introduced the division in families and used other sigla than Gleede.

α (v, o, f, p, g, e) from the digitized manuscripts, and for the manuscripts of family β (n, t, c, a, b, h) I have used previous editions. The digitized manuscripts b and h I have collated myself. The short list shows that the common textual tradition of the Greek manuscripts is strong:⁴²

Praescr.	Ἰησοῦ Χριστοῦ v o f p g e ; κυρίου Ἰησοῦ Χριστοῦ n t c a b h
1.1	ἐν τῷ κυρίῳ v o f p g e ; ἐν κυρίῳ n t c a b h
2.1	ὁσφύας ὑμῶν v o f p g e ; ὁσφύας n t c a b h ἀπολιπόντες n t c a b h g ; ἀπολειπόντες v o f p e
4.1	διδάξωμεν v o f p g e ; διδάξομεθα n t c a b h
6.2	ὑπὲρ αὐτοῦ v o f p g e ; ὑπὲρ ἑαυτοῦ n t c a b h
6.3	οἱ εὐαγγελιστάμενοι ἡμᾶς n t c a b h ; οἱ εὐαγγελιστάμενοι ὑμᾶς v o f p g e τῶν σκανδάλων v o f p g e ; σκανδάλων n t c a b h
7.2	ἀπολιπόντες n t c a b h g ; ἀπολειπόντες v o f p e
9.1	ἐν αὐτῷ v o f p g e Eus ; αὐτῷ n t c a b h

As for family α , Funk has established the succession of manuscripts v > o > f > p. On the basis of my collation of Eblatanus (e), it has become clear that it is a direct copy of Florentinus (f). In some cases, it has, against all other manuscripts, the same readings as f and p (2.1 θρόνον καὶ δόξαν; 4.1 οὐδ' ἐξενεγκεῖν; 6.3 προφηται (without article); 7.1 *om* Ἰησοῦν Χριστὸν ... μὴ ὁμολογῆ). In two instances, it has the same reading with f alone against all other manuscripts (5.2: εὐσπλαγχοι; 7.2: ἐπὶ τῶν ἐξ ἀρχῆς). The Vatican manuscript g, in turn, has some special agreements with the crown witness Vaticanus (4.3 πάντα μωμοσκοπεῖται; 7.1 μεθοδεύει; 9.1 τοῖς ἄλλοις), but here and there it also disagrees with v. Furthermore, the copyist of g is conscious of the text of Eusebius, having remarks on it in the margin.

As for the family β , Barberinus (b) and h have – as far as I can see – never been collated before. Both manuscripts are clearly members of the family but is difficult to say, whether they are copies of a single older manuscript of the family β or not.⁴³ Prostmeier has similar difficulties in tracing the source of manuscript d.⁴⁴ I think it is possible that the copyists of b and h drew either one way or another upon two manuscripts instead of one. If this suggestion is considered mere speculation, there has to be another viable explanation – if we want to keep up Funk's dominant thesis that all Greek "Polycarnabas" manuscripts must be traced back to Vaticanus. Excepting Andros (a), Parisinus (p) and Eblanus (e), all the Greek manuscripts have their *Sitz im Leben* in Italy, particularly in Vatican. Their interrelationship is tight, and most of them stem from the 16th century.

As far as I can see, there are altogether 22 Latin manuscripts of the long recension of the Ignatian letters and the letter of Polycarp (see TABLE 2). Two of these have remained unmentioned in the editions and I have found them in digital catalogues; there are no digitized images available ("unclassified manuscripts"). The digitized or otherwise collated 20 manuscripts can be divided into two families. Both families include ten manuscripts. As for family α , all manuscripts except Oxon. Magdalensis (m) have been digitized. I have collated them, including the four manuscripts not collated before (α , $\mu\alpha$, v1, v2). As for family β , six manuscripts are available in digital form, and I have collated them and particularly the two, which have not been collated before (d, m β). Lightfoot

⁴² I have not been able to collate the non-digitized manuscripts d, r, s. As stated above, d has been studied by Prostmeier. At two instances, family β offers the better reading. Note also a curiosity: manuscript g sides with family β against its own family α in reading ἀπολιπόντες pro ἀπολειπόντες (2.1; 7.3).

⁴³ Barberinus has most affinities with Trecensis (t), having at two instances the same reading against all other manuscripts (1.1 ἐνελημμένοι; 7.2 ἔστι (pro ἔστιν)). Barberinus has one notable omission (4.3 *om* περὶ τὴν τοῦ κυρίου πίστιν, ἐντυγχανούσας). On the basis of one notable reading (9.1 ἀσκεῖν πᾶσαν ὑπομονὴν b h e Eus), manuscript h is close to Barberinus.

⁴⁴ PROSTMEIER 1994, 55-57.

collated bm and bn and located them into family β but did not use them (see above). Thus, I have not been able to collate m, b and v, but for the last chapters of Pol., I have followed the collation of others.⁴⁵ In sum, I have collated nine manuscripts of family α and six manuscripts of family β . Here is the list of clearest instances of division between the two textual families:⁴⁶

- Praeser.** Philippis r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; Philippensis c r β o t c β m β
- 1.1** connexis c r β o t c β m β ; connexi r a c α p f u m α v1 v2
- 1.2** fidei vestrae r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; vestrae fidei c r β o t c β m β
- 1.3** in quod multi c r β o t c β m β (quo) ; in quem multi r a c α p f u m α v1 v2
salvi estis facti r ; estis salvi facti a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; salvi facti estis c o c β m β ; facti estis r β (*add salvi super lineam*) t
- 2.1** servite deo r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; servite domino c r β o t c β m β
credite r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; credite ergo c r β o t c β m β
cui subiecta r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; huic subiecta c r β o t c β m β
cuius sanguinem r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; huius sanguinem c r β o t c β m β
- 2.3** et quod r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; et mementote et illud quod c r β o t c β m β
- 3.2** alius similis r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; similis alius c r β o t c β m β
- 4.1** scitote ergo r c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; scitote autem a c r β o t c β m β
- 4.2** post haec etiam c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; post haec autem r a ; post haec c r β o t c β m β
- 5.1** scientes ergo r c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; scientes autem a c r β o t c β m β
deridetur r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; irridetur c r β o t c β m β
- 5.2** iustitiae eius r a c r β o t c β m β ; eius iustitiae c α p f u m α v1 v2
digne eo r a p f u m α v1 v2 ; digne c α ; digne in eo c r β o t c β m β
- 5.3** mundi r a c α p f u v1 v2 ; huius mundi m α ; om mundi c r β o t c β m β
refrenantes semet ipsos r c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; refrenantes se c r β o t c β m β
- 6.1** Et presbyteri simplices r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; Presbyteri simplices sint c r β o t c β m β
viduas et pupillos r a c α p f u v1 v2 ; viduas, pupillos c r β o t c β m β
estote ab omni avaritia r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; ab omni avaritia estote c r β o t c β m β
- 6.2** omnes r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; omnes nos c r β o t c β m β
- 6.3** sic ergo serviamus r v1 ; si ergo serviamus a c α p f u m α v2 ;
serviamus ergo c r β o t c β m β
abstinentes r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; abstinete c r β o t c β m β
- 7.2** vanitatem r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; vanitates c r β o t c β m β
sobri in orationibus et r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; sobri simus in orationibus c r β o t c β m β
ieiunia tolerantes r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; ieiunia tolerantes et c r β o t c β m β
- 8.1** indeficienter ergo r c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; ndeficienter autem a c r β o t c β m β
- 9.1** ipso Paulo et r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; Paulo et in c r β o t c β m β
- 9.2** hi omnes non r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; omnes hi non u ; non hi omnes c r β o t c β m β
- 10.2** possitis r a c α p m f u m α v1 v2 ; potestis b c r β o t c β m β v
irreprehensibilem habentes r a c α p m f u m α v1 v2 ;
considerantes irreprehensibilem b c r β o t c β m β v
- 10.3** vae autem r a p m c α f u m α v1 v2 ; vae autem illi b c r β o t c β m β v
- 11.1** itaque ut abstinenceis vos r a c α p f u m α v1 v2 ; itaque vos ut abstinenceis b c r β o t c β m β v
m u ; itaque vos ut abstinenceis vos o
- 11.2** non se abstinuerit r a c α p f c β m α v1 v2 ; se non abstinuerit m ; non abstinuerit se b c
r β o t c β m β v
aut r a p m u m α v1 v2 c α ; aut ut f ; an b c r β o t c β m β v

⁴⁵ As for Bruxellensis (b), BAUER (1995, 16; using other sigla) states that it completely agrees with Colbertinus (c) and Oxon. Balliolensis (o).

⁴⁶ Cf. GLEEDE (ref. 3, p. 364-365), who presents the readings of a and c β .

- 11.3 noveramus b c rβ o t cβ mβ v ; cognoveramus r a cα p m f u mα v1 v2
 12.2 dei filius b c rβ t cβ v ; filius o ; dei filius eius r a cα p m f u mα v1 v2
 in dominum c ; in dominum nostrum b rβ o t cβ mβ v ; in dominum nostrum et deum r
 a cα p m f u v1 ; in dominum et deum nostrum mα ; in dominum nostrum et dominum
 v2

In some of these instances, there are very slight variations within families,⁴⁷ but the evidence for division in two families is overwhelming. The six manuscripts of family β, which I have collated, have a very united profile; they all seem to be direct or second-hand copies of an early Italian manuscript. There are only a few variant readings, and the four manuscripts I have not been able to collate (b, v, bm, bn) are told to be very similar to the rest of the family.⁴⁸ The 11th-century Bruxellensis (b)⁴⁹ is the earliest of them all, and the other Brussels manuscripts bm and bn are copied from it.

The unity of family β is not quite surprising, because most of them originate in the 12th century and in the same region, in northern France and eastern Lorraine between Paris and Brussels. The oldest family β manuscript Bruxellensis (b; 11th century) can be traced back to the Benedictine Gembloux Abbey, which, from the times of abbot Olbert (1012 – 1048) was an intellectual and spiritual centre with an excellent library. Since the abbey suffered several fires in the 12th century, we cannot be sure about the precise origins of the manuscript. Colbertinus (c; from 12th century) was donated by John of Burgundy, the archbishop of Cambrai, in the 15th century to the monastery of the Celestines in Ternes. The manuscript most likely originated in a monastery of his diocese. Remensis (rβ; late 12th century), in turn, was in the possession of the cathedral of Reims. All these three manuscripts share the same content;⁵⁰ therefore, they are closely related. Trecensis (t; 12th century) originates in Clairvaux Abbey, which was founded in 1115, while Carolopolitanus β (cβ; 12th century) stems from the Cistercian monastery of Signy, which was founded in 1135. The only British manuscript of family β, Oxon. Balliolensis (o; 12th century) is from Builwas Abbey, a Cistercian monastery founded in 1135. It is likely that all these three manuscripts were produced for the libraries of these new spiritual and intellectual centres. Of the two remaining manuscripts, Vindobonensis (v; 14th century) is clearly of Italian origin; it stems from the Benedictine abbey of Santa Giustina in Padua. The case of Matritensis β (mβ; 14th century), is interesting because it belonged in the early 18th century to the collections of Philip V, the king of Spain. It is possible that it originates in a northern French or southern Flemish ecclesiastical institution that was under the Spanish crown (“Spanish Netherlands”) in the 17th century. To sum up, the manuscripts of family β – with the exception of Vindobonensis and possibly also Matritensis β – stem from the same area in the same time period. To explain their common origin, we need just one family β manuscript brought in the 11th century or earlier from Italy to Paris.

As for family α, the situation is different. To begin with, family α has only three manuscripts, which stem from the 11th or 12th century, and most of the later, 15th-century manuscripts originate in Italy. Furthermore, the history of the oldest manuscripts is somewhat complicated. The 9th-century Reginensis, which is by far the oldest manuscript we have on the letter of Polycarp (and the long

⁴⁷ One case is particularly striking. The copyist of Artabatensis (a) writes rather *autem* than *ergo*, and at three instances he joins the manuscripts of family β against his own family (4.1 *scitote autem*; 5.1 *scientes autem*; 8.1 *indeficienter autem*; cf. also 4.2 *post haec autem* (with r)).

⁴⁸ See above my review on the work of LIGHTFOOT.

⁴⁹ This manuscript originates in the Benedictine Gembloux Abbey, which, from the times of abbot Olbert (1012 – 1048) was an intellectual and spiritual center with an excellent library.

⁵⁰ They all have commentaries of Jerome and Augustin on the epistles of Paul plus the long recension of the Ignatian letters and the letter of Polycarp (in this order). Colbertinus begins with Origen’s commentaries on Paul’s letters (translated by Rufin).

recension of Ignatian letters), has a great number of deviant readings. There are altogether 17 instances, in which Reginensis stands alone against all the other manuscripts:

- 1.3 salvi estis facti r ; salvi facti estis c o cβ mβ ; facti estis rβ (*add salvi super lineam*) t ;
estis salvi facti a cα p f u mα v1 v2
- 2.1 dedit ei ; dedit r
- 4.3 circa fidem dei om r
- 5.2 neque detractores ; non detractores r
- 6.2 oculorum domini ; oculorum dei r
- 8.1 nec inventus est dolus ; nec dolus inventus est r
- 9.2 verbo iustitiae ; verbo eius r
hoc saeculum a c rβ o t cβ mα ; in hoc saeculum r ; hoc praesens saeculum cα p f u mα
v1 v2
- 11.1 contristatus sum ; contristatus r
factus est ; factus r
- 11.3 epistulae ; ecclesiae r
- 12.2 sempiternus pontifex ; sempiternus r
qui sunt ; qui r
credituri sunt ; credituri r
- 13.1 vos et Ignatius ; Ignatius et vos r
- 13.2 erat vobis profectus r
- 14.1 omnibus vestris ; omnibus vobis r

Because of the great number of scribal errors and other editorial differences, Reginensis can hardly be regarded as the common ancestor of other family α manuscripts. The closely related Artebatensis (a), which stems from the Abbey of Saint-Vaast in Pas-de-Calais and must be dated to the beginning of the 11th century, is a good (and beautiful) copy of an earlier manuscript. We find only a few instances, in which Artebatensis disagrees with all other manuscripts; two of them are of special interest:⁵¹

- 5.2 cui si complacemus r cα p f u mα v1 v2 ; cuius sicut placeamus a ;
huic si placemus c rβ o t cβ mβ
- 6.3 in hypocrisim portant cα p f u mα v1 v2 ; in hypocrisis inportant a ;
in vanum portant c rβ o t cβ mβ ; inportant r

These cases are related to the four common readings of Reginensis and Artabatensis against all other manuscripts.⁵² On the basis of the strong similarities between these two manuscripts, I find it likely that they are independent copies of one and the same Italian – most likely a Roman – manuscript.⁵³ Furthermore, the special agreements between r and a must be explained in terms of the numerous instances, in which family β as a whole has the same reading as the two oldest manuscripts of family α (r and a), while the rest of the family α as a whole has quite another reading:

- 2.1 servit r a c rβ o t cβ mβ ; deservit cα p f u mα v1 v2
- 3.2 scripsit r a c rβ o t cβ mβ ; scribo cα p f u mα v1 v2
deflectimini r a c rβ o t cβ mβ ; deflectamini cα p f u mα v1 v2
- 4.1 est avaritia r a c rβ o t cβ mβ ; avaritia est cα p f u mα v1 v2
scitote ergo cα p f u mα v1 v2 ; scitote autem r a c rβ o t cβ mβ

⁵¹ There are two minor cases: 13.2 vobis erit ; vobis erat a ; 14.1 habebitis ; habetis a

⁵² 3.3 omnium vestrum r a ; 4.2 post haec autem r a ; 5.3 virgines autem et casta r a ; 9.2 eum qui ; cum r a

⁵³ Artabatensis seems to have been a copy of a copy of the Italian manuscript.

- nosmet r a c rβ o t cβ mβ ; nos cα p f u mα v1 v2
- 5.1 scientes ergo cα p f u mα v1 v2 ; scientes autem r a c rβ o t cβ mβ
- 5.2 iustitiae eius r a c rβ o t cβ mβ ; eius iustitiae cα p f u mα v1 v2
- 5.3 virgines autem in immaculata et casta cα p f u mα v1 v2 ; virgines autem et casta r a ;
virgines in casta c rβ o t cβ mα
- 6.1 abstinete vos r a c rβ o t cβ mβ ; abstinete cα p f u mα v1 v2
- 7.1 martyrium cα p f u mα v1 v2 ; mysterium r a c rβ o t cβ mα
- 8.1 indeficienter ergo cα p f u mα v1 v2 ; indeficienter autem r a c rβ o t cβ mβ
Iesus Christus cα p f u mα v1 v2 ; Christus r a c rβ o t cβ mβ
- 9.2 hoc saeculum a c rβ o t cβ mα ; in hoc saeculum r ;
hoc praesens saeculum cα p f u mα v1 v2
- 10.1 prestantes cα p m f u mα v1 v2 ; praestolantes r a c rβ o t cβ mβ
- 13.2 de his cα p m f u mα v1 v2 ; de ipsis r a c rβ o t mβ cα

The hitherto uncollated 12th-century manuscript Carolopolitanus α (cα) is the oldest among the family α manuscripts; its variant readings must stem from a different manuscript than the common source of Reginensis and Artabatensis. Like Carolopolitanus α, all the later manuscripts of family α also replace a part of a long sentence (sic ergo serviamus ... domini nostri Iesu Christi) from 6.3 to 6.2 (after *dimittere*). Another interesting case is already mentioned above: in 6.3, cα reads *in hypocrisis portant* and is followed by later manuscripts of family α. Reginensis has *important*, Artabatensis *hypocrisis inportant*, and manuscripts of family β all read *in vanum portant*.

Carolopolitanus α stems from the abbey of the Premonstratensians – founded in 1133 – in Belval-Bois-des-Dames (Belval) in northern France, in the diocese of Reims and close to the Belgian border. Just like Artabatensis, this manuscript seems to have been a second-hand copy of an Italian manuscript, which already included the peculiar characteristics listed above. It is not surprising that in some cases, the Carolopolitanus α seems to have preserved the original reading of the Latin translation, particularly in reading *ergo* (< οὐν) against *autem* in 4.1; 5.1 and 8.1. In 5.3, *virgines autem in immaculata et casta conscientia* corresponds the Greek original ἐν ἀμώμῳ καὶ ἀγνῇ συνειδήσει. In 7.1 cα preserves the original reading *martyrium crucis* (<τὸ μαρτύριον τοῦ σταυροῦ) against *mysterium crucis*, and in 8.1 *Iesus Christus* (<Χριστὸς Ἰησοῦς) is the original reading (against *Christus*).⁵⁴ The secondary readings introduced by cα are mostly stylistic, but there is also one misinterpretation of the original Latin text (3.2: scripsit, “he (Paul) has written” > scribo “I (Polycarp) will write”). Only one conclusion is possible: Carolopolitanus α is a copy of a different manuscript than Reginensis and Artabatensis. All these three manuscripts, however, seem to have the same or at least very similar grandfather or great-grandfather. In 16th-century Italy, the old manuscript behind Carolopolitanus α was copied several times. Some of the manuscripts we know (p m f u mα v1 v2) are direct and some second-hand copies from this interesting representative of family α.

Furthermore, there is also another specific development of variants within family α. There are several readings, which can be found only in the 15th-century manuscripts p, f, u, mα – and m, which I was unable to collate:

- 1.1 congratulatus : congratus p f u
ostendistis ; ostendisti a ; ostendis p f u
- 2.1 in veritate ; in vanitate p f u⁵⁵
- 2.2 quae ipse ; quem ipse p f u
- 2.3 miserebitur vestri ; miserebitur vobis p f u mα

⁵⁴ The likely original readings of cα, for which we do not have the Greek text, are 10.1 prestantes and 13.2 de his.

⁵⁵ These manuscripts exhort readers to serve God “in fear and vanity”.

3.1	vos provocastis ; nos provocastis p f
6.2	debemus etiam ; debemus et p u
7.2	verbum ; verborum p f u m̄ nos inducat ; vos inducat p f u
8.2	credidimus ; credimus p f u m̄
9.1	oculata fide ; occulta fide f u m̄ [r ante cj] in beatissimis illis ; in his beatissimis p f u
9.2	in vacuo ; in vano p f u
10.2	ex bonis ; ex omnibus f m
11.2	qui ; quae m f u m̄
12.2	aedificet ; deficiet f ; deificet p u m̄ ⁵⁶ in omni mansuetudine ; omni mansuetudine p f m

In one way or another, these 15th-century manuscripts are chronologically and – at least in some ways – locally interrelated. Palatinus, Florentinus and Urbanus originate in Italy, but I have not been able to clarify the background of Oxon. Magdalensis. The 15th century Matritensis α (m̄) was from very early on in the possession of Juan de Torquemada (1388 – 1468), who was in Paris in 1415 – 1430, before becoming the Prior of the Dominican house in Valladolid. It is possible that he brought this manuscript with him from Paris. The simplest explanation for the peculiarities of these manuscripts would be that they were all produced in Italy or directly in Rome. A study of their readings in the long recension of the Ignatian letters would be helpful.

The readings of these five manuscripts (p, f, u, m, m̄) also reveal that manuscripts v1 and v2 are not dependent on any of them, but most likely directly on the Italian ancestor of Carolopolitanus α. Manuscripts v1 and v2 share common readings all the way through, and they have very few singular readings. Furthermore, the abbreviations they both use in Pol. 3.3 shows that they are interrelated:

mensura mensi fueritis, eadem remetietur ; men. m. f. e. r. (v1) ; m. m. f. e. r. (v2)
quoniam ipsorum est regnum ; q. ill. e. r. (v1) ; q. i. e. r. (v2)

Unlike the Greek manuscripts, most known Latin manuscripts including the long recension of the Ignatian corpus and the letter of Polycarp have their home outside Italy. It is interesting to note that none of them has ended up in a German library. Instead, we can conclude that at least half of the manuscripts we know were produced in northern France and many of them were copied for the needs of the new monasteries, which were about to become spiritual and intellectual centres of the region. Also, the 12th-century British manuscript, Oxon. Balliolensis (o) may stem – directly or indirectly – from a manuscript, which at the time was available in Paris.

In his commentary of the letter of Polycarp, Johannes Bauer points out – against the dating to the early Middle Ages by Funk and others – that the language of the Latin translation of the letter is that of the patristic age and that there are traces of the Old Latin translation of the Bible.⁵⁷ On the basis of linguistic arguments and comparison to *Passio Sancti Ignatii*, which is dependent on Pol., Gleede dates the Latin translation of Pol. very early, already into the late 4th or early 5th century. However, we do not know anything about the early history of Latin translation.

⁵⁶ The databases of Latin Christian texts show that deification was a theologically relevant topic, not only in the East, but also in the West; see ORTIZ, Jared, ed. *Deification in the Latin Patristic Tradition*. Washington DC: The Catholic University of America Press 2019.

⁵⁷ BAUER 1995, 17-18.

To sum up, all Latin manuscripts including the long recension of the Ignatian letters and the letter of Polycarp stem from three early medieval Italian (Roman?) manuscripts. One of them was the father or grandfather of the Roman Reginensis (9th century) and the northern French Artabatensis (11th century), which was read by the monks of the Abbey of Saint-Vaast in Pas-de-Calais. The second one can be traced back to the 12th century (*terminus ad quem*); one of its copies – Carolopolitanus α – belonged to the abbey of the Premonstratensians in Belval-Bois-des-Dames (Belval) in the diocese of Reims. The very same Italian manuscript was copied and recopied by scribes, who produced the later, 15th-century manuscripts family α we know. The third lost ancient manuscript is the 10th or 11th-century archetype of all the known manuscripts of family β .

In this article, I have tried to show how digitized manuscripts can or could influence scholarship today. After the great work of Dressel, Zahn, Funk and Lightfoot, the essential question of the original text of the letter of Polycarp was settled for the 20th century. Most scholars may think that the later textual history of the early Christian writings – with the notable exception of the New Testament – is rather a curiosity, which has nothing to do with exegetical and historical questions related to the documents. However, knowing something about the history of the manuscripts may lead to answers to other kinds of questions – questions of the scribal practices and scribal theology, the spreading of the early Christian writings in medieval Europe, the interrelation between manuscripts and documents in the learned world, the local texts and their impact, and the like. Finally, reading these manuscripts is a rich cultural and spiritual experience.

APPENDIX. “Apostolic Fathers” as a Designation and as a Collection of Books

New Testament is the first library of Christianity. For the Christians of the first three centuries, the canon of the New Testament was more practical than a systematic entity. In the second century, the four Gospels and most letters carrying the good name of the Apostle Paul were considered authoritative. Only in the latter half of the fourth century, Athanasius counted all 27 books of our New Testament to the canonical writings. To be sure, the authority of the Hebrews remained disputed in the West, while the Eastern orthodox Christians remained skeptical about the divine authority of the book of Revelation.

While the four Gospels and the letter of Paul were transmitted and gaining authority, the Christian teachers of the second century also had a need to emphasize that the teaching of the Apostles continued to be unchanged in the Church after their death. In this regard, it was important to emphasize that the followers of the Apostles taught with the authority of the Apostles: although they as teachers were not on the same level, they all taught the very same doctrine as the Apostles, and their teachings should be valued. Among other things, the use of the term *ἀποστολικός* demonstrates this. Ignatius of Antioch greets the church of Trallis in an “apostolic way,” and in the martyrdom of Polycarp, this bishop of Smyrna says that he is “an apostolic teacher and prophetic bishop” (Mart. Pol. 16.2).

Already in the late second century, Christian authors referred to the time after the Apostles with the expression *post apostolorum tempora*. The first reference we know of stems from Tertullian who emphasizes that the heresies appeared only after the Apostles’ time.⁵⁸ The historical perspective was deepened by Eusebius of Caesarea. He characterizes Clement (Hist. eccl. 5.6.2) and Polycarp (3.36.1) as disciples of the Apostles. Eusebius says that Justin flourished as a Christian teacher “not long after

⁵⁸ Adv. Marc. 1.21: “Quodsi post apostolorum tempora adulterium veritas passa est circa dei regulam, ergo iam apostolica traditio nihil passa est in tempore suo circa dei regulam, et non alia agnoscenda erit traditio apostolorum quam quae hodie apud ipsorum ecclesias editur.”

the Apostles” (2.13.2); similarly, he also says that Hegesipp, who was active in the second half of the second Century, lived in the first post-apostolic generation (2.23.3). Eusebius mentions that he is not even able to list all the teachers of Christian communities who came after the Apostles (3.37.4).

Already the first Christian teachers were called “fathers”. Paul, for example, tries to persuade the quarrelling Corinthian Christians to his side (1 Corinthians 4:15): “For though you might have ten thousand guardians in Christ, you do not have many fathers. Indeed, in Christ Jesus I became your father through the gospel.” Ignatius leans on this tradition when he guides Trallian Christians to respect the deacons as Jesus Christ and the bishop, “who is the model of the Father” (Ign. Trall. 3.1). Polycarp is described as an Asian teacher and father of Christians in a martyrdom story written about him (Pol. Mart. 12.2), and the Apostolic constitutions emphasizes the power of the bishop in strong words (2.26.4): “He is the teacher of piety; and, next after God, he is your father, who has begotten you again to the adoption of sons by water and the Spirit.”

Eventually, in the writings of John Chrysostom, both bishops and priests appear as the fathers of Christians. The expression “Churches Fathers” (οἱ ἐκκλησιαστικοὶ πατέρες, οἱ πατέρες τῆς ἐκκλησίας) can be traced back to the practices of the victorious Church of the 4th century, and Eusebius of Caesarea is the first author we know to have employed this expression (Adv. Marcellum 1.4.3; 2.4.21; De eccl. theol. 1.14.2). It is a broad and comprehensive expression that encloses all Church teachers considered to be truly Nicean, all who were regarded as followers of the teachings of the Apostles.

Church fathers also speak of the “apostolic men” (οἱ ἀποστολικοὶ ἄνδρες, viri apostolici). Clement of Alexandria uses this expression only once and so occasionally (Strom. 2.20.118) that its use cannot actually be derived from his texts. The expression was introduced by Eusebius of Caesarea, who in his Church History refers with it to the Apostles, especially to Peter, who were seen and praised by Philo in Rome (hist. eccl. 2.17.2; 2.18.7). Eusebius also says that Ignatius knew Polycarp as an “apostolic man” (Hist. eccl. 3.36.10).⁵⁹ Referring to the early Christian teachers who were not Apostles, Jerome also, who used Eusebius as his source, speaks about “apostolic men”, such as Luke (Ep. 57.10) and Apollo (Ep. 65.1). As for men who flourished after the Apostles, this designation is deserved for Ignatius of Antioch (Contra Pel. 3.2), Clement of Rome (Comm. in Is. 14.52), and Irenaeus of Lyon (Comm. in Is. 17.64). Through the popular works Eusebius and Jerome, these expressions spread widely among medieval writers among Eastern and Western Christian authors.

In the patristic times, both words “apostolic” and “fathers” were heavily used, but surprisingly seldom together. In the whole Greek corpus of Christian writings, we encounter the term “Apostolic Fathers” only twice. The fourth document of the Third Council of Constantinople (680 – 681) refers to the truth of faith as “conveyed by the Apostles and Apostolic Fathers” (ὡς παρὰ τῶν ἀποστόλων καὶ τῶν ἀποστολικῶν πατέρων παρεδόθη).⁶⁰ In his book *Hodēgos* (“Guidebook”), Anastasius of Sinai calls Dionysius Areiopagita “Apostolic Father” (13.4: ὁ ἀποστολικὸς πατὴρ Διονύσιος ὁ Ἀρεοπαγίτης; cf. 22.3; 24.1; 24.1).⁶¹

However, these two texts are not enough to demonstrate that the expression “Apostolic Fathers” would have been current. From the 8th century onwards, medieval texts of the Eastern Church refer

⁵⁹ Eusebius himself also calls Polycarp an apostolic and prophetic teacher (Hist. eccl. 4.15.39). The name διδάσκαλος ἀποστολικός is very rare in the texts and ecclesiastical documents of the churches, while ἀποστολικὴ διδασκαλία occurs often.

⁶⁰ RIEDINGER, Rudolf. *Acta conciliorum oecumenicorum Series secunda, volumen secundum: Concilium universale Constantinopolitanum tertium*. Pars 1-2. Berlin: De Gruyter, 1990 – 1992. P. 52.

⁶¹ See the edition of UTHEMANN, Karl-Heinz. *Anastasius Sinaitae viae dux*. Corpus Christianorum. Series Graeca 8. Turnhout: Brepols, 1981. P. 3-320.

at several occasions to the teachings of the Apostles and Fathers who followed them in order to emphasize the unity of the Christian doctrine; in particular, the terms ἀποστολικός and πατέριος often appear together. The common use of “Fathers” and “Church Fathers” as technical terms and the idea of the unity of the Christian doctrine in the first centuries made it unnecessary to talk about “Apostolic Fathers” as a specific group of early Christian teachers. When the reform movements of the 16th century challenged the doctrinal tradition of the Catholic Church, the teachers of the Church responded that the Church and its doctrine have remained the same from the times of Christ and his Apostles.

In the Church of the West, Eusebius’ Church History was known as the translation of Rufinus, which transmitted the historical knowledge of the teachers in the post-apostolic times. Referring to the early times of Christian history, it was simple to talk about the time “after the Apostles”. Thus, for example, Martin Luther uses the term *post apostolorum tempora* or *post tempora apostolorum*; in a sermon from 1532, he describes the change in the practice of the baptism and refers to the fathers after the times of the Apostles (*patres post tempora apostolorum*).⁶² Luther saw the interpretations of Church fathers in the light of his *sola scriptura* principle and in the light of his own theology of justification. Therefore, he was often forced by his Catholic opponents to set them against the teaching of the Church fathers and to conclude that the fathers have often been wrong.⁶³ Philipp Melancthon saw the difference between the first two centuries and the doctrinal evolution of the ensuing period. He expressed doubts about the theology of Origen, with its allegorizing exegesis and philosophical speculations. He saw in Origen the spiritual ancestor of Pelagius, the heretic of the Catholic West.⁶⁴ The reformers were not particularly interested in the writings of the second-century teachers, because they were not able to find there any articulate teachings for their own actual debates about the trinity, baptism and Eucharist.

The use of the designation “Apostolic Fathers” begins among protestant authors of post-Reformation England, and it was first used as a synonym for some more popular expressions. The designations “ancient Fathers” and “primitive Fathers”, which are becoming more common in the 16th century, generally refer to the authoritative teachers of the first centuries. “Fathers of the Church” also appears as a common expression in English texts from the time of reform. The term “Apostolical Fathers”, in turn, is rare, but it was used in the 16th and 17th centuries occasionally, in a total of 33 works. By way of comparison, the term “Apostolical men”, inherited from Eusebius, appears in a total of 504 works in that period.⁶⁵

The protestant authors tended to reserve the expression “Apostolical Fathers” for the Fathers who were immediate followers of the Apostles. The very first witness for the use of this designation is Richard Taverner (n. 1505 – 1575), who in a sermon from 1540 (on 1. Peter 2) exhorted the Roman Christians to lead an honest life among the Gentiles, “...whych thyng in dede came to passe in the primatiue church by the godly exemple of the good Apostolicall fathers and christen people in Rome and els where.”⁶⁶ Christopher Rosdell, in a tractate defending the Reformation, refers to “many exhortations, both of Christ and his Apostles, and also of the Apostolicall fathers which succeeded

⁶² LUTHER, Martin. *D. Martin Luthers Werke: kritische Gesamtausgabe*. (Weimarer Ausgabe [WA]). Weimar 1883 - 2009. WA 36, p. 108.

⁶³ LUTHER, Martin. *Contra Henricum regem Angliae*. [1522], WA 10/2, 182-183.

⁶⁴ FRAENKEL, Peter. *The Function of the Patristic Argument in the Theology of Philip Melancthon*. Geneva: Librairie E. Droz, 1961. P. 82-90.

⁶⁵ This information as well as the early English texts quoted here are based on the database *Early English Books Online* (EEBO).

⁶⁶ TAVERNER, Richard. *The Epistles and Gospelles with a brief postil vpon the same from after Easter tyll Aduent, which is the somer parte set forth for the singuler co[m]moditie of all good Christen men and namely of prestes and curates*. [London], 1540. P. 42a.

them, not onely by order of place, but also veritie of doctrine.”⁶⁷ The catholic authors, in turn, tended to use it as a synonym for the Fathers of the Church, i. e. for the authoritative teachers of the Church of its first five centuries. One example of this can be found in the writings of the Protestant convert into Catholicism Hugh-Paulin (Serenus) de Cressy (1605 – 1674), who during the Civil War was exiled in France and acted there for the Catholic cause in England. In his work *Exomologesis* he designates all Church Fathers, starting from Clement of Rome and Ignatius of Antioch, as Apostolical Fathers.⁶⁸ It is therefore not surprising that the French Catholic scholar J. B. Cotelier who in 1672 published the first collection of these earliest Fathers resisted of using the simple designation, which he most likely knew and entitled his book *Patres, qui temporibus Apostolicis floruerunt*.⁶⁹ It was the protestant author William Wake who in 1693 first used the expression “Apostolical fathers” in the title of his translation: *The genuine epistles of the apostolical fathers, S. Barnabas, S. Ignatius, S. Clement, S. Polycarp, the Shepherd of Hermas, and the martyrdoms of St. Ignatius and St. Polycarp*.⁷⁰ As the title demonstrates, Wake limited his work to the authors of the second century.

LITERATURE

I have collected here all the printed literature, which is not available through my research guide mentioned in the note 2.

BAUER, Johannes Baptist. *Die Polykarpbriefe. Kommentar zu den Apostolischen Vätern* 5. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck u. Ruprecht 1995.

de CRESSY, Hugh-Paulin. *Exomologesis, or, A faithfull narration of the occaision and motives of the conversion unto Catholick unity*. Paris, 1653.

EHRMAN, Bart (ed. and trans.), *The Apostolic Fathers*. Vols. 1-2. Loeb Classical Library 24-25. Harvard University Press 2003.

FRAENKEL, Peter. *The Function of the Patristic Argument in the Theology of Philip Melancthon*. Geneva: Librairie E. Droz, 1961.

FUNK, Franz Xaver. Der Codex Vaticanus gr. 859 und seine Descendenten. *Theologische Quartalschrift* 62 (1880), p. 629-637.

GLEEDE, Benjamin. *Parabiblica Latina: Studien zu den griechisch-lateinischen Übersetzungen parabilischer Literatur unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der apostolischen Väter*. Vigiliae Christianae, Supplements 137. Leiden: Brill 2016.

⁶⁷ ROSDELL, Christopher. A godlie and short discourse shewing not onely what time the inhabitants of this land first receyued the Christian faith: but also what maner of doctrine was planted in the same. London, 1589. P. 13v.

⁶⁸ de CRESSY, Hugh-Paulin. *Exomologesis, or, A faithfull narration of the occaision and motives of the conversion unto Catholick unity*. Paris, 1653. P. 181–182. On de Cressy see also LINCICUM, David. The Paratextual Invention of the Term ‘Apostolic Fathers’. *JTS* 66, 2015. P. 142.

⁶⁹ *Patres, qui temporibus Apostolicis floruerunt* Barnabae, Clementis, Hermae, Ignatii, Polycarpi. Opera edita et inedita, vera, & supposititia; una cum Clementis, Ignatii, Polycarpi, actis atque martyriis. David Lincicum has traced the copies of Cotelier’s work in European libraries and observed that in the British libraries its title has often been abbreviated into form *Patres apostolici*. Lincicum suggests that this abbreviation has inspired William Wake to use the expression “Apostolical Fathers”.

⁷⁰ David LINCICUM (ref. 67, p. 143–148) has traced the copies of Cotelier’s work in European libraries and observed that in the British libraries its title has often been abbreviated into form *Patres apostolici*. Lincicum suggests that this abbreviation has inspired William Wake to use the expression “Apostolical Fathers”.

HARTOG, Paul. *Polycarp's Epistle to the Philippians and the Martyrdom of Polycarp: Introduction, Text, and Commentary*. Oxford University Press 2013.

von, HEFELE, Karl Joseph. "Patrum apostolicorum opera." ThQ 21, 1839, p. 341-348.

de JONGE, Henk Jan. *On the Origin of the Term 'Apostolic Fathers'*. JTS 29, 1978, p. 503-505.

LINCICUM, David. The Paratextual Invention of the Term 'Apostolic Fathers'. JTS 66, 2015, p. 139-148.

van, LIT, L.W.C. (O.P.), *Among Digitized Manuscripts*. Philology, Codicology, Paleography in a Digital World. Leiden: Brill 2020.

LUTHER, Martin. *D. Martin Luthers Werke: kritische Gesamtausgabe*. (Weimarer Ausgabe [WA]). Weimar 1883 - 2009.

ORTIZ, Jared, ed. *Deification in the Latin Patristic Tradition*. Washington DC: The Catholic University of America Press 2019.

PROSTMEIER, Ferdinand 1999. *Der Barnabasbrief*. Übersetzung und Kommentar. Kommentar zu den Apostolischen Vätern. Ergänzungsreihe zum Kritisch-exegetischen Kommentar über das Neue Testament, Bd. 8. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht 1999.

RIEDINGER, Rudolf. *Acta conciliorum oecumenicorum Series secunda, volumen secundum: Concilium universale Constantinopolitanum tertium, Pars 1-2*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 1990 – 1992.

ROSDALL, Christopher. *A godlie and short discourse shewing not onely what time the inhabitants of this land first receyued the Christian faith: but also what maner of doctrine was planted in the same*. London, 1589.

TAVERNER, Richard. *The Epistles and Gospelles with a brief postil vpon the same from after Easter tyll Aduent, which is the somer parte set forth for the singuler co[m]moditie of all good Christen men and namely of prestes and curates*. [London], 1540.

UTHEMANN, Karl-Heinz. *Anastasius Sinaitae viae dux*. Corpus Christianorum. Series Graeca 8. Turnhout: Brepols, 1981, p. 3-320.

Résumé

For some 25 years, more and more medieval manuscripts have been digitized, and scholars can – or at least could – consult digitized catalogues and digital libraries. In light of the manuscripts and editions of the so-called Apostolic Fathers, I would like to demonstrate what kind of concrete research materials and research options this change can offer. The epistle of Polycarp studied here is of particular interest because half of this epistle is preserved only in Latin manuscripts, which have been seldom studied by modern scholars.

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